

OPTIMIZATION OF SPEECH COMPETENCE IN CHILDHOOD

Jo‘rayeva Mohira Yunus qizi

Qarshi davlat universiteti doktoranti

joraevamohira71@gmail.com +998919559809

Annotation: This article deals with the process of speech development and optimization of language skills in childhood. The problems of speech competence are analyzed and solutions are given in the article.

Key words: Childhood education, skills, stages of speaking skill, flipchart media.

Early childhood education is education done by giving various stimulations to help growth and children’s development both physical and spiritual so that children themselves have readiness to enter next education level. Through early childhood education, children expected to be able to develop all potentials contained in the child included morale development and spiritual values, physical, social, emotional, language, art and craft included inside of the children. One of the early childhood development aspects is language development aspect. One’s language development skills must be stimulated since early so language ability in human can develop optimally suitable with stage of the child’s age. Language skill is required to be given proper handling so it can develop appropriate with stage of the one’s age.

The success of language development can influence reading skill, listening, writing and speaking skill. Language skill in the children must be given the training, one of it is speaking skill which can make vocabulary increased so children are not having struggle when communicate with people surround them. Children who are able to speak well will deliver children who has high confident. So it will push cognitive abilities that children have. Besides that, children who have good speaking skill will avoid them from speech delay.

Children speaking skill has several stages, such as

- 1) Prelinguistic Speech (Speaking through sound but without words by the age of 0-11 months),
- 2) Linguistic Speech (speaking with one word speech by the age of 12-18 months),
- 3) Making Words into Phrases (Making words into phrase by the age 2-3 years old),
- 4) Using Complete Sentences (using complete sentences by the age 4-6 years old) and
- 5) Using Language Symbolically Reading and Writing (use language symbolically by the age 6-8 years old).

Children who are given interesting activities can improve speaking skill, then children will get experience in communicate in their life, like can reveal their feeling, reveal the ideas they have, can give information and can socialize with their

environment. Learning activities on early childhood must be as interesting as possible so the learning activity can be succeeded and elevate children speaking skill. Interesting activity can be created through learning media. Learning media can be said as a tool that can be intermediary in learning activity (Mursid, 2015). One of the learning media is flipchart media. Flipchart media expected to be one of the learning media that can optimize children speaking skill. In optimize children speaking skill can be done through flipchart media. Flipchart which content provided by researcher and teacher in helping improve children speaking skill. Flipchart media designed as attractive as possible so it will make children’s study interest increase and children speaking ability can develop well appropriate with the level of their development. This is strengthen by research result done by Marsita, Anggria Negara, Oka, etc with title “Implementation of Assisted Storytelling Flipchart Media Method Can Develop Children’s Oral Language Skill by the Age of 5-6 Years Old” which proves that children oral language skill increases after implementing flipchart media in learning activity.

Speaking skill is individual ability in communicate and deliver everything contained in thought and its feeling so people around him know what he need and what he tries to deliver. Speaking ability also has influence toward one’s academic development. This is because children who have speaking skill well can do discussion activity and deliver the result that has been discussed clearly and easy to understand by hearer. So this is the important of optimize early childhood speaking skills. One of the optimize children speaking skill done by flipchart media learning which can attract child’s interest in paying attention of learning activity take place. Flipchart media is pieces which has same size, bound well together which in it has been designed by researcher and teacher so that can be used to improve children speaking skill.

There are also two different but interrelated sets of skills of language: receptive and expressive language. Both are necessary for communication.

Receptive language (comprehension) is about understanding what is being communicated. It involves keeping track of the visual, written, auditory and social cues of the environment. For instance, seeing keys and understanding that your friend is going out; looking out for signs around like “stop”; hearing the bell and comprehending it is recess time; seeing the mother smiling and understanding she is praising you. To be able to comprehend, one must listen, pay attention, concentrate, follow gestures (nonverbal language) and facial expressions (changes in the face according to emotions), recognize social interaction rules (when to talk, when to listen) and follow instructions.

Expressive language refers to sharing thoughts, needs, ideas and emotions using words. It involves labeling objects by their names, describing things, forming

sentences with right grammatical forms, telling stories, answering questions and other skills similar to these. Receptive language skills are required for healthy development of expressive language. A person should first understand language and what is being communicated. Then, they can convey their messages. There are different ways for expression. Speaking, writing, using gestures or sign language or other assistive technology devices are the most common ways.

At this stage children begin to develop and enhance skills related with **reading, writing and grammar**. More specifically, children between these ages are expected to master skills in the list below:

- Being able to form much longer and more complex sentences
- Most of the grammar is acquired (passive tense, comparative words, compound sentences)
- Understanding inferences and more abstract uses of language (predicting results, drawing conclusions, understanding jokes or riddles etc.)
- Understanding the difference between factual (what really happened) and theorized (what could have happened and why) information
- Can read, understand and retell stories
- Using language to give opinions, show support or disagree with the others (presenting reasons for agreement or disagreement etc.)
- Starting conversations with other people, following the natural flow of interaction, making eye contact and taking turns
- Summarizing, organizing and presenting information (can understand and express using their own way)

LITERATURE:

1. Ade Karunia Rizky Manurung. University Negeri Jakarta. October 21, 2019; accepted December 7, 2019.
2. Duygu Tüzün. Clinical Psychologist and PhD Researcher. 2023
3. Canadian Paediatric Society (2017). Screen time and young children: Promoting health and development in a digital world.
4. Bonamy, r. (2016). Social cognition and conduct problems a development approach. *Journal of the american of child and adolescent psychiatry* vol 50 issues 4 , 385-994.
5. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.
6. Ochilovich, S. Z., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. *FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA*, 1(2), 89-99.